

ORTHOPTEROIDEA FAUNA OF LESOTHO

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Abstract

In total, 134 species in 110 genera and 20 families of the former cohort 'Orthopteroidea' were recorded in Lesotho. All records (localities, data of collection, information source) in Lesotho are listed for each species. In southern Africa, the numbers are higher by an order of magnitude, which may indicate how much of the Lesotho fauna is unrecorded. The most speciose order of 'Orthopteroidea' in Lesotho is Orthoptera (93 species within 77 genera), and the most speciose family within this order is Acrididae (62 species within 45 genera). All families of 'Orthopteroidea' recorded in southern Africa are listed, and the number of species and genera are given separately for the whole subcontinent and Lesotho to elucidate how much is known about Lesotho fauna. At least 10 species of 'Orthopteroidea' are endemic to Lesotho: *Hyposphaeria guillamodi*, *Oxypilus inscriptus*, *Conocephalus basutoanus*, *Gymnogrillus politus*, *Basutacris inflatifrons*, *Eremidium basutho*, *Qachas fastigiata*, *Sphingonotus basutensis*, *Xiphocera fissa*, and *Brachyphymus basuto*.

KEYWORDS: Orthoptera, Distribution, endemics, Maloti/Drakensberg 'hot spot'

Introduction

Ten insect orders: Blattodea (including Termitoidea), Mantodea, Dermaptera, Plecoptera, Phasmida (=Phasmatodea), Orthoptera, Grylloblattodea, Mantophasmatodea, Embioptera, and Zoraptera were formerly grouped in a cohort, the Orthopteroidea (=Polyneoptera). Six of these orders have representatives in Lesotho fauna: Blattodea, Mantodea, Dermaptera, Plecoptera, Orthoptera, and Phasmida. The fauna of these orders is, however, poorly known. For example, no data on Lesotho species are available in Scholtz & Holm (1985); Cigliano *et al.* (2019) lists only 24 species of Orthoptera from Lesotho, including 15 species of Acrididae and two of Pyrgomorphidae; only four species of Mantidae for Lesotho and no species of Phasmida are listed by Patel & Singh (2016) and Brock (2022).

The famous taxonomist Francis Walker (1809-1874) from the British Museum was the first to study the Lesotho fauna in the second half of the 19th century. Although jealous contemporaries criticized his careless taxonomic

descriptions, he described almost 20,000 new insect species from all over the world, most of which are still valid (Graham 1979). Fifteen of them from Lesotho are representatives of the former cohort 'Orthopteroidea', including seven species from the family Acrididae and three species from the family Tettigoniidae.

Lesotho 'orthopteroid' fauna was later investigated during 1950-51 by members of Lund University from Sweden. A collection made by these researchers constituted a basis for several taxonomic works (e.g. Chopard, 1955; Beier, 1955a; Dirsh, 1956; Hincks, 1957; Princis, 1963). In 1959, Brown (1963) organized an expedition to Lesotho to collect members of Orthoptera. In the 1950s and 1960s, two Soviet entomologists based in the United Kingdom, Vitaly Mikhailovich Dirsh (1904-1982) and Boris Petrovich Uvarov (1889-1970), carried out thorough taxonomic studies on Acrididae deposited mainly in the British Museum in London. They described several new species from Lesotho.

From the end of the 20th century onwards, Orthoptera species from Lesotho have been the subject of taxonomic studies by two American entomologists, D. Otte and P. Naskrecki. Daniel Otte, from the Academy of Natural Sciences of Drexel University, Philadelphia (PA), studies mainly Acrididae, and Piotr Naskrecki, from the Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University (Cambridge, MA), mainly studies Tettigoniidae.

This paper aims to bring together all data on the occurrence of species from the former cohort 'Orthopteroidea' ever recorded in Lesotho and place them in the modern systematic and nomenclature.

Study Area

The Kingdom of Lesotho is an enclave (30,300 km²) within the Republic of South Africa. It is drained by the Orange River (Senqu) and its four major tributaries, the Malibamatso, Senqunyane, Makhalleng, and Mohokare (Caledon). Most of the country (3/4) is located in the Maloti/Drakensberg Mountains (above 1,800 m a.s.l.) covered mainly with *Themeda-Festuca* mountain grassland (Afroalpine and Afroalpine grasslands). *Cymbopogon-Themeda* (Highveld) grassland is the natural vegetation in the lowlands (below 1,800 m a.s.l.) (Fig. 1 A-B). Today, however, most of the lowlands have been converted to arable lands and villages (Fig. 1 C-D). Rainfall is concentrated (85%) in summer (October-April) with 600-800 mm in lowlands, and 800-1,200 mm in highlands annually (Ambrose *et al.* 2000).

The Maloti/Drakensberg Mountains is a 'hot spot' region (c. 40,000 km²). About half of its area is in Lesotho (Ambrose *et al.*, 2000). About 1,750 vascular plant species were recorded in this region, with 1/3 being endemic. Similarly high is the endemism of invertebrate fauna (Kopij, 2000, 2006).

Materials and Methods

Most of the checklist is compiled from literature records. An attempt was made to adapt their old names to those currently accepted in zoological nomenclature and to place them in modern systematic order (Cigliano *et al.*, 2019). Records from Lesotho were retrieved from all published sources of information scattered in scientific journals worldwide (e.g., Walker, 1870; Beier, 1953; Chopard, 1955; Dirsh, 1956; Hincks, 1957; Brown, 1962; Holier, 2012). In addition, the following major works were consulted: Naskrecki (1994, 1996), Naskrecki & Bazeleta (2009, 2011, 2012), Naskrecki *et al.* (2009), Massa (2017) (Tettigoniidae); Dirsh (1951, 1956a, 1956b, 1961, 1965a, 1965b) (Acrididae); Otte (1955, 2015) (Acridoidea); Green (1998) (Acrididae); Jago (1971, 1994) (Acrididae); Johnston (1956) (Acrididae); Mungai (1992) (Acrididae); Uvarov (1966, 1977) (Acrididae); Townsend (1983) (Gryllotalpidae); Kevan (1956); Kevan & Hsiung (1985) (Pyrgomorphidae); Grunshaw (1995) (Acrididae); Stevens & Picker (1995) (Plecoptera); Samways & Sergeev (1997) (Orthoptera); Deyriese (1999) (Tetrigidae); Holier (2012) (Acridoidea); Anon. (2015, 2022) (Orthopteroidea); Brock *et al.*

(2016) (Phasmida); Popov *et al.* (2019) (Acrididae); Cigliano *et al.* (2019), accessed on 01.12.2023 (Orthoptera).

From 1996 to 2002, the author of this paper (National University of Lesotho) collected 'Orthopteroidea' specimens in various parts of the country. The following keys and field guides were used for species identification: Uvarov (1966, 1977), Scholtz & Holm (1985), Townsend (1983), Pricker *et al.* (2002). His collections were deposited in the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, Poland. Some collections were also made in the Katse and Mohale dams' catchment areas at the end of the 1990s and early 2000s as a part of the Lesotho Highland Water Project and were deposited in South African museums.

The number of recorded species and genera in Lesotho are compared with those recorded in southern Africa (a region south of the Zambezi and Cunene rivers) to show what is known about the Lesotho fauna. This was done to facilitate further investigations of the orthopteroid fauna in this endemic region of Africa. Numbers of species and genera recorded in southern Africa are taken chiefly from Beccaloni (2014), Anon. (2015, 2022), Cigliano *et al.* (2019), and Brock *et al.* (2022).

Figure 1. Lesotho, A) highlands around the Semonkong Waterfall; B) foothills around the Popa Mountain; C) lowlands (lowland/foothill borderline) in Roma Valley; D) lowlands along the sandstone cliffs in Nazareth.

Systematic checklist of species

The following data are given for each species and include the valid Latin (scientific) name with the author and year of description (if the species was recorded in Lesotho under a different name, this name [synonym] is also given), localities, record dates (reference, i.e., the source of these records, author and year of publication for literature records, surname only for an unpublished record), and information on species occurrence outside Lesotho (for South Africa, provinces where species were recorded are listed as follows: CP – Cape Province, WC – Western Cape, EC – Eastern Cape, NC – Northern Cape, FS – Free State, KZN – KwaZulu Natal, T – Transvaal). In the case of Lesotho holotypes, information is also provided on depository institutions.

All localities of Lesotho records are listed in Table II and Fig. 4. For each locality, a quarter-degree grid (about 24 km x 27.5 km; Fig. 4) is given, as used elsewhere in Lesotho (Kopij, 2000, 2006).

Order Blattodea

The order includes cockroaches with 6 families, 500 genera, and 4,600 species worldwide, and termites (Termitoidea) with 9 families with 3,000 species in 30 genera worldwide. The cockroach fauna of southern Africa is represented by 231 species within 57 genera and 6 families. The most speciose genera in this region include *Hyposphaeria* (24 spp.), *Pseudoderopeltis* (22 spp.), *Xosablatta* (13 spp.), *Euandrobatta* (11 spp.), and *Deropeltis* (11 spp.) (Beccaloni, 2014). Most species are restricted to the more humid southern and eastern parts of southern Africa. Twenty genera are endemic (Picker *et al.*, 2002). Southern African termite fauna is represented by 210 species in 50 genera and 5 families (Mbata, 2018). The Lesotho fauna is poorly investigated. To date, 20 species of cockroaches in 13 genera and 4 families have been recorded. Only a single termite species is known from Lesotho.

Family Blattidae

***Blatta orientalis* Linnaeus 1758**

Lesotho, general, 1998-2002, G. Kopij.

Distribution: cosmopolitan.

***Cartoblatta aeroniger* (Rehn 1922)**

Mt. Moorosi, 16.03.1951, Princis 1963; Mamathes, 24.03.1952, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN, T; Namibia.

***Deropeltis erythrocephala* (Fabricius 1781)**

Mahlatsa, 11.02.1951, 30.12.1951, 20.04.1952, Princis 1963; Mamathes, 15.02.1952, 27.03.1952, 19.04.1952, Princis 1963; Mt. Machake, 25.03.1951, Princis 1963; Teyateyaneng, 24.04.1952, Princis 1963; Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Princis 1963; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Namibia.

***Deropeltis intermedia* Brunner von Wattenwyl 1865**

Quthing, 15.03.1951, Princis 1963; Mt. Moorosi, 16.03.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN; Mozambique.

***Periplaneta americana* Linnaeus 1758**

Lesotho, general, 1998-2002, G. Kopij.

Distribution: cosmopolitan.

***Pseudoderopeltis bimaculata* (Walker 1868)**

Mamathes, 03.03.1952, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN; Mozambique, Malawi.

***Pseudoderopeltis foveolata* (Walker 1868)**

Mamathes, 07.11.1952, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP; Zimbabwe.

***Pseudoderopletis montana* Princis 1963**

Mamathes, 22.08.1948, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), Princis 1963; Mahlatsa, 01.01.1953, Princis 1963; Mosoeling, 20.04.1952, Princis 1963; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1952, Princis 1963; Quthing, 15.03.1951, Princis 1963; Dikolobeng River, 16.03.1951, Princis 1963; Senqu River (13 km W of Quthing), 17.03.1951, Princis 1963; Morija, 22.03.1951, Princis 1963; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Princis 1963; Mt. Machake, 25.03.1951, Princis 1963; Teyeteyaneng, 28.03.1951, Princis 1963; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

Family Blattellidae=Ectobiidae

***Blatella germanica* (Linnaeus 1767)**

Lesotho, general, 1998-2002, G. Kopij.

Distribution: cosmopolitan.

***Diptertrum bicolor* (Kirby 1900)**

Quthing, 15.03.1951, Princis 1963; Mt. Moorosi, 16-18.03.1951, Princis 1963; Morija, 22.03.1951, Princis 1963; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Princis 1963; Makheke, 07.04.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP.

***Pseudoceratinoptera magrinalis* Hanitsch 1937**

Mahlatsa, 01.1952, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN, T; Namibia, Mozambique.

***Temnopteryx quadriglumis* Princis 1963**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

Family Blaberidae

***Gyna caffrorum* Stal 1856**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002.

Distribution: all over southern Africa.

***Hyposphaeria basuto* (Princis 1963) = *Perisphaeria basuto* Princis 1963**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), Princis 1963; Makheke Mts., 07.04.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

***Hyposphaeria bicolor* (Saussure et Zahrtner 1895) = *Perisphaeria bicolor* Saussure et Zahrtner 1895**

Mosoeling, 20.04.1952, Princis 1963; Mamathes, 23.12.1951, 15.02.1952, 19.04.1952, Princis 1963; Mahlatsa, 30.12.1951, 01.01.1955, Princis 1963; Quthing, 15-17.03.1951, Princis 1963; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

***Hyposphaeria guillarmodi* (Princis 1963) = *Perisphaeria guillarmodi* Princis 1963**

Mamathes, 07.10.1951, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), Princis 1963; Mamalapi Mts., 27.12.1948, Princis 1963.

Distribution: Lesotho only.

***Pilema fusca* (Burmeister 1838)**

Mamathes, 22.01.1949, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, T.

***Pilema reflexa* (Walker 1868)**

Mopeli River (64 km E of Maseru), 02.03.1956, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T.

***Pilema thoracica* (Walker 1868)**

Mamathes, 27.02.1949, 18.04.1949, 05.1950, 03.03.1951, 29.03.1951, 18-24.04.1952, 04.05.1952, 31.12.1952, Princis 1963; Moeling, 20.04.1952, Princis 1963; Mahlatsa, 30.12.1951, Princis 1963; Quthing, 15.03.1951 Princis 1963; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Princis 1963.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, T.

Family Pseudophyllodromiidae

***Supella (Supella) dimidiata* (Gersaecker 1869)**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002.

Distribution: all over Africa.

Family Termitidae

***Trinervitermes trinervoides* Sjoestedt 1911**

Lesotho, general, G. Kopij.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, FS, KZN, T; Namibia, Zimbabwe, Mozambique.

Order Mantodea

Praying mantises (Mantodea) include 33 families, 460 genera, and c. 2,400 species worldwide; 1,261 species are within the family Mantidae (Petal & Singh, 2016). Praying mantises occurring in southern Africa are representatives of 285 species in 69 genera grouped into five families: Hymenopodidae, Mantidae, Thespidae, Sibyllidae, and Empusidae (Picker *et al.* 2002). Lesotho fauna is represented by 14 species of praying mantises in 13 genera and 3 families.

Family Hymenopodidae

***Harpagomantis tricolor* (Linnaeus 1758)**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over South Africa.

Family Mantidae

***Bolbella punctigera* (Stal 1871)**

Quthing, 12-17.03.1951, Beier 1953.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, Comoro Is.

***Chroicoptera saussurei* Guglio-Tos 1915**

Quthing, 11-15.03.1951, Beier 1955a; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Beier 1955a.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T.

***Entella rudebecki* Beier 1955**

Quthing, 14.03.1951, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), Beier 1955.

Distribution: Lesotho only.

***Epioscopomantis chalybea* Burmeister 1838**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over South Africa.

***Harpagomantis tricolor* (Linnaeus 1758)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Beier 1955; Mt. Hodimonate, 17.03.1951, Beier 1955a; Quthing, 17.03.1951, Beier 1955a; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Beier 1955a.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN.

***Ligaria (Ligaria) quadrinotata* Chopard 1914**

Maseru (Lancer's Gap), 22.03.1951, Beier 1955a; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Beier 1955a; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Beier 1955a.

Distribution: South Africa: T; Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Zambia, Kenya, Ethiopia.

***Miomantis fenestrata* (Fabricius 1781)**

Quthing, 11-14.03.1951, Beier 1955a; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Beier 1955a.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP; Namibia, Mozambique, Congo, Ruwenzori, Somalia.

***Miomantis coxalis* Saurse 1898**

Lesotho, general, Patel & Singh 2016.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T; Namibia, Angola.

***Oxypilus (Anoxypilus) inscriptus* Beier 1955**

Quthing, 15.03.1951, holotype (IZ, Lund Univ.), Beier 1955a.

Distribution: Lesotho only.

***Polyspilota aeruginosa* (Goeze 1778) Fig 2A.**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over South Africa.

***Popa spurca spurca* Stal 1856**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Sphodromantis gastrica* Stal 1858**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: southern and eastern Africa.

Family Empusidae

***Empusa guttula* (Thunberg 1815)**

Mamathes, 11-15.02.1945, Beier 1955a; Mt. Moorosi, 03.04.1951, Beier 1955a

Distribution: FS, CP, KZN, T.

Order Dermaptera

Earwigs are hemimetabolous, nocturnal scavenger insects with 12 families and c. 2,000 species worldwide: 4 families in southern Africa and two families in Lesotho.

Family Pygidicranidae

***Esphalmenus peringueyi* (Bormans 1900)**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Hincks 1957.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN.

***Nala lividipes* (Dufour 1820)**

Quthing, 15.03.1951, Hincks 1957; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Hincks 1957.

Distribution: cosmopolitan (Africa, Mediterranean Europe, India, Philippines, Australia, Central America); common, invasive, agricultural pest.

Family Labiduridae

***Labidura riparia* Pallas 1783**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: cosmopolitan.

***Euborellia annulipes* (Lucas 1847)**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: cosmopolitan.

Order Plecoptera

Stoneflies are primitive insects with nymphs living in clean water. There are 15 families and c. 3,500 species worldwide; 2 families in southern Africa: Perlidae (>5 spp. in the genus *Neoperla*) and Notonemouridae (40 spp. in southern Africa) (Picker *et al.*, 2002). Two species in a single genus were hitherto recorded in Lesotho.

Family Notonemouridae

***Balinskycercella gudu* (Balinsky 1956)**

Qiloane Waterfall (Makhaleng River), 07.01.1955, Stevens & Picker 1995.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN.

***Balinskycercella tugelae* (Balinsky 1956)**

Oxbow, 21.01.1990, Stevens & Picker 1995.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN.

Order Phasmida

The stick and leaf insects are divided into 13 families. The order includes 3,481 species worldwide (Brock *et al.*, 2022), mostly tropical. In southern Africa, c. 50 species in 14 genera and 5 families were recorded, with only one species in Lesotho (Picker *et al.*, 2002).

Family Diapheromeridae

***Bactrododema reyi* (Grandidier 1869) = *Palophus reyi* Fig. 2E**

Lesotho, general, Pricker *et al.* (2002), G. Kopij.

Distribution: all over South Africa.

Order Orthoptera

The order has two suborders: Ensifera (13 families) and Caelifera (28 families). The former includes two infraorders: Gryllidea with 6 families and Tettigoniidea with 7 families. The latter also has two infraorders: Acrididea with 27 families and Tridactylidea with a single family. Worldwide, there are 28,312 spp. within 5,208 genera (by 15 September 2022; Cigliano *et al.*, 2019). In southern Africa, there are 10 families in Ensifera (including 7 in Tettigoniidea) and 10 in Caelifera (including 8 in Acridoidea). Acrididae is the largest family, with more than 6,700 species worldwide, arranged in 26 subfamilies and 4 clades (Song *et al.*, 2018). In grassland ecosystems, grasshoppers contribute more than half of the arthropod biomass in the aboveground grass layer (Gillon, 1983). They exert a significant ecological impact in grasslands in terms of nutrient cycling (Mitchell & Pfadt, 1974; Belovsky & Slade, 1993; Gangwere *et al.*, 1997) and provide an important source of nutrition for both invertebrates (Joern *et al.*, 2006) and vertebrates (Gandar, 1982), thus supporting other biological components of the ecosystem (Belovsky & Slade, 1993). Grasshoppers can also be excellent monitors of landscape use as they are ecologically sensitive and yet sufficiently mobile and abundant to serve as bioindicators (Samways & Sergeev, 1997; Gebeyehu & Samways, 2002; Bazelet & Samways, 2014). To date, 93 species in 77 genera and 8 families were recorded in Lesotho.

Subordo Ensifera

Family Gryllidae

***Arachnocephalus bidentatus* Chopard 1951**

Maseru, 27.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: DRC (Kivu).

***Gryllus bimaculatus* De Geer 1773**

Approximately 24 km northern of Matatiele, 07.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Quthing, 05.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Dikolobeng River (18 km NE of Quthing), 14.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: widespread and common in southern Africa; also widespread in southern Europe, the Middle East and the Oriental region.

***Brachytrupes politus* Bolivar 1890**

Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Quthing, 12.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: Tanzania. The record from Lesotho requires confirmation.

***Oecanthus capensis* Saussure 1878 Fig. 2H**

Maloti Mts., 1929, Toms & Otte 1988; Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: southern, eastern, and central Africa.

Family Gryllotalpidae

***Gryllotalpa africana* Palisot de Beauvois 1805 Fig. 2F**

Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: widespread and common in Africa; also, Portugal, India, and Pakistan.

***Gryllotalpa devia* Saussure 1877**

Mamathes, 08.05.1949, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

Family Anostomatidae

***Onosandrus splendens* Sjöstadt 1913**

Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Nazareth, 24.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, Tr.

Family Tettigoniidae

***Arytropteris granulithorax* Peringuey 1916**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

***Conocephalus (Conocephalus) basutoanus* Chopard 1955**

Qachas Nek, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), 08.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: Lesotho only.

Figure 2. A) *Polyspilota aeruginosa*, B) *Gryllus bimaculatus*, C) *Terpinistria zebrata*, D) *Conocephalus caudalis*.
 E) *Bactrododoma reyi*, F) *Gryllotalpa africana*, G) *Plangia graminea*, H) *Oecanthus capensis*.

Conocephalus (Anisoptera) caudalis (Walker 1869) Fig. 2D

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002.

Distribution: all over South Africa.

Ruspolia consobrina (Walker 1869) = Homorocoryphus deminutus Chopard 1955

Maseru, 22.03.1951, Chopard 1955; Hansley's Dam, 30.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: all over southern Africa.

Plangia graminea (Serville 1838) Fig. 2G

Lesotho, general, von Wattenwyl 1878.

Distribution: all over southern and eastern Africa.

Terpnistria zebrata (Seville 1838) Fig. 2C

Lesotho, general, G. Kopij.

Distribution: all over South Africa. Tanzania, Mozambique, Zambia.

Tylopsis continua (Walker 1869)

Quthing, 17.03.1951, Chopard 1955.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN; Namibia, Mozambique, Zambia, DRC.

Suborder Caelifera

Family Acrididae

Acanthacris ruficornis (Fabricius 1787)

Quthing, 15.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, May 2022. R. Rudland.

Distribution: CP, KZN, T; Madagascar, Zambia, Eritrea, Togo; virtually throughout Africa; common.

Acrida acuminata Stal 1873

Approximately 32 km N of Matatiele, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Dikolobeng River (18 km NE of Quthing), 16.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T; Zimbabwe, Zambia, Tanzania, Congo, Kenya.

Acrida bicolor (Thunberg 1815) Fig. 3F

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 24.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: all over Africa, Mediterranean Europe and Middle East.

***Acrida propingua* Burr 1902**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 14.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T; Botswana, Zimbabwe.

***Acrida sulphuripennis* (Gerstaecker 1869)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: widespread in Africa.

***Acrida testacea* (Thunberg 1815)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T; Namibia, Botswana.

***Acrotylus furcifer* Saussure 1888**

Mamathes, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1951, 28-29.03.1951; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 12-15.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN; Zimbabwe, Zambia.

***Acorypha pallidicornis* (Stal 1876)**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 10.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN, T; Namibia, Zimbabwe, Angola, Zambia, Malawi, Tanzania, Kenya, Somalia.

***Aiolopus thalassinus* (Fabricius 1781)**

Hansley's Dam, 30.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: widespread in Africa, Europe and SW Asia, China, Australia, Pacific Islands.

***Anablepia dregeri* (Ramme 1929)**

Approximately 32 km N of Matatiele, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

***Anacridium moestum* (Serville 1838)**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over South Africa.

***Anaelopus dorsalis* (Thunberg 1815) = *Anaelopus socius* (Stal 1873)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; 32 km N of Matatiele, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 14-17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1954, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; Makheke Mts., 08.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: FS, CP, KZN, T; Mozambique, Malawi.

***Aneuryphymus erythropus* (Thunberg 1815)**

Lesotho, general, Cigliano *et al.* 2019.

Distribution: South Africa: CP.

***Anthermus granosus* Stal 1878**

Mamathes, 18.02.1949, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN, T; Zimbabwe, Angola, Tanzania, western Africa.

***Brachyacrida distantii* Dirsh 1952**

Maseru, 24.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T.

***Brachyphymus basuto* Dirsh 1956**

Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, T.

***Calliptamicus semiroseus* (Serville 1838)**

Lesotho, general, Walker 1870a.

Distribution: all over southern Africa.

***Calliptamulus hyalinus* Uvarov 1922**

Lesotho, general, Johnstone 1968.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, FS, T.

***Calliptamulus natalensis* (Sjöstedt 1913)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T.

***Calliptamulus sulfurescens* Uvarov 1922**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, FS, KZN, T.

***Cannula gracilis* (Burmeister 1838) Fig. 3F**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Catantops melanosticus* Schaum 1853**

Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN, Mozambique; apparently widespread in Africa.

***Coryphosima stenoptera vicina* (Dirsh 1956) = *Paracomacris vicina* Dirsh 1956**

Approximately 32 km N of Matatile, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: species: all over Africa; subspecies: South Africa: CP.

***Cyrtacanthacris aeruginosa* (Stoll 1813) Fig. 3C**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 24.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Malealea, 30.04.2017, W. Lewis.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN; Namibia, Angola, DRC, Congo, Tanzania, Chad, western Africa.

***Dnopherula obliquifrons* (Bolivar 1912) = *Aulacobothrus obliquifrons* Bolivar 1912**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN; Zimbabwe, Zambia, Angola, DRC, Congo, Tanzania, Kenya, Uganda.

***Duronina chloronata chloronata* (Bolivar 1912) = *Duronina chloronata* (Stal 1876)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Durinia chloronata curva* Uvarov 1953 = *Durinia curta* Uvarov 1953**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; 32 km N of Matatile, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 12-17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 24-26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Hansley's Dam, 30.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, T; Zimbabwe, DRC.

***Euryphymus haematopus* (Linnaeus 1758)**

Lesotho, general, Cigliano *et al.* 2019.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, FS, T.

***Gastrimargus acutangulus* (Stal 1873)**

Tetateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, T; Angola, Tanzania, Ivory Coast.

***Gastimargus crassicollis* (Saussure 1888) = *Gastrimargus clepsydrae* Sjostedt 1928 = *Gastrimargus crassipes* Sjostedt 1928**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 24.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 16.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: WC, EC, T; Zimbabwe.

***Gymnbothrus carinatus* Uvarov 1941**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T.

***Gymnbothrus lineaalba* Bolivar 1889**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Heteropternis minor* (Saussure 1899) = *Heteropternis saussurei* Kirby 1902**

Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: T; Zambia, Angola, DRC, Tanzania, Kenya.

***Heteropteris thoracica* (Walker 1870)**

Lesotho, general, Dirsh 1956

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Locustana pardalina* (Walker 1870)**

Maseru, 27.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, T; Namibia, Angola, Zambia, Comor Is.

***Morphacris fasciata* (Thunberg 1815)**

Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 14.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: Africa, southern Europe, Middle East, India.

***Nomadacris septemfaciata* (Serville 1838)**

Lesotho, general, Grunshaw 1995.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Oedaleus nigrofasciatus* (De Geer 1773) Fig. 3B**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 12-15.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Senqu River (13 km W of Quthing), 03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN; Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Uganda, western Africa.

***Oedaleus plenus* (Walker 1870)**

Quthing, 15.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyaneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, T; Namibia, Botswana, Tanzania.

***Orthochtha dasyncnemis* (Gerstaecker 1869)**

Lesotho, general, Popov & Fishpool 1992.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Paracinema tricolor tricolor* (Thunberg 1815)**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; 32 km N of Matatiele, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Hansley's Dam (described as *P. t. sylvestris* Thunberg 1815 is synonymous with *P. t. tricolor*), 30.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN; Malawi, Tanzania, Kenya, Uganda, DRC, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Liberia.

***Pheocatantops rosaceus* (Uvarov 1942) = *Pheocatantops decoratus rosaceus* Uvarov 1942**

Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution of the species: South Africa: T; Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Zambia, DRC, Tanzania, Uganda, Kenya, Ethiopia.

***Platacanthoides bituberculatus* Uvarov 1922**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Moorosi, 16.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 25.02.1959, Brown 1962; 60 ml S of Maseru, 27.02.1959, Brown 1962.

Distribution: South Africa: FS.

***Platacanthoides reductus* Dirsh 1956**

Quthing, 17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP.

***Pnorisa squalus* (Stal 1861)**

Quthing, 17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Hansley's Dam, 20.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: widespread in Africa.

***Pycnodictya flavipes* Miller 1932**

Mamathes, 10.04.1949, 08.01.1950, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: T.

***Rhachitopsis crassus* (Walker 1870)**

Lesotho, general, Cigliano *et al.* 2019.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T; Namibia.

***Rhachitopsis ceraseus* Uvarov 1922**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Hansley's Dam, 20.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; 16 km S of Teyateyaneng, 18.12.1951, Dirsh 1956; 24 km w of Maseru, 07.01.1959, Dirsh 1963; 10 ml S of Teyateyaneng, 18.12.1958, Brown 1962; 15 ml. N of Maseru, 07.01.1959, Brown 1962; Mokhotlong, 25.02.1959, Brown 1962.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP; Namibia; very common in the Karoo (Brown 1962).

***Rhaphotittha cephalica* Bolivar 1914 = *Pseudoacryptera cephalica* (Bolivar 1914)**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, KZN, T; Zimbabwe, Angola, Tanzania, Kenya.

***Rhaphotittha palpalis* (Uvarov 1929) = *Pseudoacryptera palpalis* (Uvarov 1929)**

32 km N of Matatle, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; 8 km W of Mokhotlong, 25.02.1959, Brown 1962.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP.

***Scintharista saucia* (Stal 1873) = *Conistica saucia* (Stal 1873)**

Mt. Moorosi, 16.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP; Namibia.

***Sphingonotus (Sphingonotus) basutensis* (Dirsh 1956) = *Wernerella basutensis* Dirsh 1956**

Mt. Hodimonate, 18.03.1951, holotype (ZI, Lund Univ.), Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: type locality only.

***Sphingonotus (Sphingonotus) scabriculus* Stal 1876**

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over South Africa, Namibia.

***Vitticatantops fasciatus* (Karny 1907) = *Catantops fasciatus* Karny 1907**

Mt. Hodimonate, 12.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Quthing, 14-15.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN; Zimbabwe, Zambia, Malawi, Tanzania.

Vitticatantops humeralis* (Thunberg 1815) = *Catantops humeralis

Lesotho, general, Picker *et al.* 2002

Distribution: all over South Africa.

***Trilophidia conturbata* (Walker 1870) = *Trilophidia angustipennis* (Kirby 1902)**

Quthing, 14.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Senqu River (13 km w of Quthing), 17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T; all over Africa; Middle East.

***Tmetonota terrosa* Saurssure 1888**

Mokotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T.

***Xiphocera reflexa* (Walker 1870) = *Xiphocera fissa* Saussure 1887**

Lesotho - general, Hollier 2012.

Distribution: all over southern Africa.

Family Lentulidae

***Basutacris scotti* Dirsh 1953**

Nyakosuba, no date, holotype (MMNH London), Dirsh 1953 (p.162); Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; Makhehe Mts., 08.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maletsynyane Waterfall, 19.02.1959, Brown 1962; Malealea, 27.02.1959, Brown 1962; 46 km E of Maseru, 28.02.1959, Brown 1962; Mamathes, 07.01.1949, 10.04.1950, 11.02.1951, Brown 1962.

Distribution: South Africa: FS. Activity period in Lesotho: August-April; probably two generations.

***Basutacris inflatifrons* Brown 1962**

Semonkokong, holotype (TM, Pretoria), Brown 1962.

Distribution: Lesotho only.

***Eremidium (Eremidium) basutho* Brown 1962**

Approximately 8 km SW of Mokhotlong, 25.02.1959, holotype (TM, Pretoria), Brown 1962.

Distribution: type locality only.

***Lentula obtusifrons* Stal 1878**

Qachas Nek, 07.04.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Semonkong, 19-21.02.1959, Brown 1962; Maletsunyane Waterfall, 19.02.1959, Brown 1962.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN, T; Mozambique. Feeding on various species of Asteraceae.

***Qachasi fastigiata* Dirsh 1956**

Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, holotype (n. gen.; ZI, Lund Univ.), Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: type locality only.

Family Pamphagidae

***Pagopedilum martini* Bolivar 1915**

Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN.

***Hoplolopha reflexa* (Walker 1870)**

Lesotho, general, Dirsh 1958.

Distribution: South Africa: T.

Family Pamphagidae

***Pagopedilum martini* Bolivar 1915**

Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: KZN.

***Hoplolopha reflexa* (Walker 1870)**

Lesotho, general, Dirsh 1958.

Distribution: South Africa: T.

Family Pyrgomorphidae

***Afrosphena picticeps* (Bolivar 1904) = *Parasphena picticeps* Bolivar 1904**

Quthing, 12-17.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Maseru, 22.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Teyateyeneng, 28.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Hansley's Dam, 30.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, T.

Figure 3. A) *Pyrgomorpha granulata*, B) *Oedaleus nigrofasciatus* C) *Cyrthacantacris aeguginosa*. D) *Phymateus morbillosus*, E) *Cannula gracilis*, F) *Acrida bicolor*.

***Dictyophorus spumans* (Thunberg 1787)**

Mokhotlong, 03.11.2017, R. Rudland.

Distribution: south Africa, Zimbabwe, Mozambique.

***Parasphenella meridionalis* (Kevan 1956) = *Parasphenoides meridionalis* Kevan 1956**

Nyakosuba, 18.19.02.1929, holotype (BMNH, London), Kevan 1956; 48 km E of Maseru, 28.02.1959, Brown 1962; Mamathes, 14.10.1951, Brown 1962.

Distribution: South Africa: FS. Common in Lesotho lowlands in damp situations.

***Phymateus karschi* Bolivar 1904**

Mafeteng district, 12.11.2018, M. Mairal.

Distribution: all over Africa.

***Phymateus (Maphyteus) leprosus* = *Maphyteus (Maphyteus) leprosus* (Fabricius 1793)**

Mt. Moorosi, 18.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 24.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: South Africa: CP, KZN, T; Ethiopia.

***Phymateus (Phymateus) morbillosus* (Linnaeus 1758) Fig. 3D**

Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: widespread in Africa.

***Pyrgomorpha (Phymelloides) granulata* Stal 1875 Fig. 3A**

Maseru, no date, Kevan & Hsiung 1985.

Distribution: all over southern Africa, Angola, DRC, eastern Tanzania.

***Pyrgomorpha (Pyrgomorpha) minuta* Kevan 1863**

Roma, no date, Kevan & Hsiung 1985.

Distribution: South Africa: FS, CP, KZN; Swaziland, Mozambique.

***Zonocerus elegans* (Thunberg 1915)**

Forma *brachyptera*: 32 km N of Matatiele, 08.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Dikolobeng river (17 km NE of Quthing), 16.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Forma *macroptera*: Qachas Nek, 07.03.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: all over Africa; the form *brachyptera* and *macroptera* should be put under the same species, as this is only a wings-length trait, which is not species-specific.

Family Tetrigidae

***Paratettix scaber* (Thunberg 1815)? = *Paratettix meridionalis* (Rambur 1838)**

Mt. Machache, 25.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Nazareth, 25-26.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mamathes, 29.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Hansely's Dam, 30.03.1951, Dirsh 1956; Mokhotlong, 06.04.1951, Dirsh 1956.

Distribution: *P. scaber* is widespread all over southern Africa. *P. medidionalis* is a Palearctic species (recorded in North Africa, southern Europe, and the Middle East). *P. meridionalis* is very similar to *P. scaber* but differs by the ringed post-tibia (Devrise *et al.*, 2023). All records of this species in Lesotho, as well as in other parts of southern Africa, most probably are referring to *P. scaber*.

Discussion

A few 'Orthopteroidea' orders (Grylloblattodea, Mantophasmatodea, and Zoraptera) have been hitherto not recorded in Lesotho. Four Orthoptera families, species that commonly occur in southern Africa (Gryllacrididae, Thericleidae, Pneumoridae, Tridactylidae), have not been recorded in Lesotho so far. Species that are rare and have restricted ranges are certainly unrecorded.

Most probably, the following species may occur in Lesotho: *Acrotylus patruelis* (Herrich-Schaeffer 1838), *Gastrimargus determinatus* (Saussure 1888), *Gymnobothrus pallus* (Miller 1932) *Gymnobothrus hemipterus* (Miller 1932), *Metaxymecus gracilipes* Brancsik 1895, *Oedaleus senegalensis* (Krauss 1877), *Rhabbdoplea munda* Karsch 1893. All these species are from the family Acrididae. Two very widespread and common Tetrigidae species, *Hedotettix pulchellus* Bolivar 1887 and *Dasyleurotettix infaustus* Walker 1871, are also presumed to occur in Lesotho.

As expected, Lesotho (Maloti) shows a relatively high level of endemism for 'Orthopteroidea' species. The following species were hitherto recorded in Lesotho only: *Persiphaeria guillarmodi* (Dictyoptera: Blattodea: Blaberidae), *Oxypilus inscriptus* (Dictyoptera: Mantodea: Mantidae), *Conocephalus basutoanus* (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae), *Gymnogryllus politus* (Orthoptera: Gryllidae); *Basutacris inflatifrons* (Orthoptera: Lentulidae); *Eremidium basutho* (Orthoptera: Lentulidae); *Qachas fastigiata* (Orthoptera: Lentulidae); *Sphingonotus basutensis* = *Wernerella basutensis* (Orthoptera: Acrididae); *Xiphocerca fissa* (Acrididae). *Brachyphymus basuto* (Orthoptera: Acrididae) has been erroneously regarded (Cigliano *et al.*, 2019) as endemic to Lesotho. Almost nothing is known about these species. Most of them are from the Acrididae and Lentulidae families. The latter family is especially interesting in this regard. Most species recorded in southern Africa occur in forests, but in Lesotho, most species occur in the shrubby, bushy vegetation on the slopes along the Clarens sandstone cliffs. Tettigoniidae species may also be associated with this vegetation. Endemic species from the family Acrididae can be envisaged in the *Festuca-Themedra* alpine grasslands. The subfamily Truxalinae (Acrididae) may have many representatives in the *Festuca-Themedra* mountain grasslands.

In Lesotho, the region known as Maloti is the richest in abundance of species. The Afroalpine *Themedra-Festuca* grassland is expected to harbor the highest number of endemic and, as yet, undescribed species. All kinds of wetlands/marshlands are expected to attract most species in this vegetation type.

Conclusion

In total, 134 species in 110 genera and 20 families of 'Orthopteroidea' have been recorded in Lesotho. The family Acrididae comprises almost half of all these taxa (Table I). In southern Africa, the numbers are higher by an order of magnitude, indicating how much of Lesotho's fauna is still unrecorded.

More research is needed, especially in Tettigoniidae, Lentulidae, Pamphagidae, and Tetrigidae. Places around Mokhotlong, Thaba Tseka, Semonkong, and Quthing are easily accessible by tarred roads today and may be explored in the summer months. In winter (June-September), mountain *Festuca-Themedra* grasslands, especially the Alpine grassland, are covered with snow.

Table I. Number of species and genera in various taxa of Orthopteroidea in Lesotho, southern Africa, and the world

Taxon	Lesotho		Southern Africa	
	species	genera	species	genera
BLATTODEA	20	13	441	109
COCKROACHES	20	13	231	57
Blattidae	8	5	34	9
Blattellidae	4	4	73	19
Blaberidae	7	3	80	19
Ectobiidae	0	0	19	7
Pseudophyllodromiidae	1	1	4	2
Nocticolidae	0	0	1	1
TERMITES	1	1	210	52
Kalotermitidae	0	0	11	5
Hodotermitidae	0	0	2	2
Rhinotermitidae	0	0	7	3
Termitidae	1	1	190	39
MANTODEA	14	13	285	69
Hymenopodidae	1	1	5	4
Mantidae	12	11	239	47
Thepsidae	0	0	11	2
Sibyllidae	0	0	1	1
Empusidae	1	1	4	3
DERMAPTERA	4	4	48	25
Hemimerida	0	0	1	1
Pygidicranidae	2	2	8	6
Labiduridae	2	2	10	7
Labiidae	0	0	5	3
Forficulidae	0	0	11	2
PLECOPTERA	2	1	44	6
Perlidae	0	0	23	1
Notonemuridae	2	1	21	5
PHASMIDA	1	1	50	14
Bacillidae	0	0	43	9
Phasmatidae	0	0	1	1
Diapheromeridae	1	1	4	2
Lonchodidae	0	0	2	2
ORTHOPTERA	92	77	963	354
ENSIFERA	16	12	344	118
Gryllidae	4	4	123	42
Gryllotalpidae	2	1	4	1
Mogoplistidae	0	0	7	5
Rhaphidophorida	0	0	2	1
Schizodactylidae	0	0	8	1
Anostostomatidae	1	1	42	9
Gryllacrididae	0	0	9	3
Stenopamatidae	0	0	4	1
Tettigoniidae	7	6	155	55
CAELIFERA	76	55	619	236
Acrididae	62	45	300	114
Lathiceridae	0	0	4	3
Lentulidae	4	5	58	26
Lithidiidae	0	0	13	4

Table I – continued

Pamphagidae	2	2	69	20
Pamphagodiidae	0	0	4	4
Euschmitidae	0	0	9	4
Thericleidae	0	0	70	24
Pneumoridae	0	0	17	9
Pyrgomorphidae	9	6	39	9
Tetrigidae	1	1	24	14
Tridactylidae	0	0	12	5
Total	134	109	1831	577

Numbers for southern Africa are mostly taken from Beccaloni (2014); Anon. (2015, 2022); Cigliano *et al.* (2019), and Brock *et al.* (2022).

Table II. List of localities (see Fig. 4)

Locality	District	Atlas grit
Dikolobeng River (= Sebapala)	Quthing	73A
Hensley's Dam,	Hotse	14C
Mahlatsa,	Berea	23D
Mamalapi Mts.	Berea	34A
Mamathes (= Mamathe)	Berea	23A
Maseru	Maseru	31/32
Mokhotlong	Mokhotlong	38A
Mopeli River,	Hotse	14B
Morija	Maseru	42C
Mosoeling	?	?
Matatle = Matelile	Mafeteng	52A
Mt. Hodimonate	Quthing	72D
Mt. Machache (= Machache, Mt. Machake, Makhake Mts.)	Maseru	33BD
Mt. Makhele ?	?	?
Mt. Moorosi	Quthing	73B
Nazareth	Maseru	33C
Oxbow	Buta Bute	16B
Qacha's Neck	Qacha's Neck	66B
Quthing	Quthing	72D
Qiloane Waterfall	Maseru	34C
Teyateyaneng	Berea	22/23

Figure 4. Map of Lesotho with sheet numbers (see Table II). Each sheet covers an area of 15' latitude and 15' longitude, i.e., c. 660 km² in surface. The letters A, B, C, D attached to each sheet, as it is in Table II, refer respectively to NW, NE, SW and SE squares of the sheet (atlas grit)

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ФАУНА ЛЕСОТА – ORTHOPTEROIDEA

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Извод

У Лесоту су у оквиру бивше групе „Orthopteroidea“ забележене 134 врсте из 110 родова и 20 фамилија. За сваку регистровану врсту су наведени сви релевантни подаци (локалитети, подаци о збирци, извор информација). Најзаступљенији ред Orthopteroidea у Лесоту је Orthoptera са 93 врсте из 77 родова, а најбројнија врстама је фамилија Acrididae са 62 врсте из 45 родова. Најмање 10 врста Orthopteroidea је ендемично за Лесото: *Persiphaeria guillarmodi*, *Oxypilus inscriptus*, *Conocephalus basutoanus*, *Gymnogryllus politus*, *Basutacris inflatifrons*, *Eremidium basutho*, *Qachas fastigiata*, *Sphingonotus basutensis*, *Xiphocerca fissa*, *Brachyphymus basuto*.

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